

Development of mono and bimetallic Ru, Re catalysts for sustainable aviation fuel production (1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/064)

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is created for research application No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/064 "Development of mono and bimetallic Ru, Re catalysts for sustainable aviation fuel production" supported by Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027. Main aim of the Postdoctoral fellowship is dedicated to development of novel mono (Ru, Re) and bimetallic Ru-Re catalysts on acidic supports for production of renewable hydrocarbons with biojet fuel composition from lipid feedstocks via catalytic hydrotreatment (HT). The main objectives of the project involve:

- 1) Synthesize, characterize and conduct catalytic screening tests of mono Ru, Re and bimetallic Ru-Re HT catalysts supported on different acidic supports;
- 2) Upgrade catalyst characteristics to achieve improved and reusable performance in lipid feedstock conversion into RH with biojet fuel composition;
- 3) Evaluate improved catalyst ability to convert different lipid wastes;
- 4) Establish optimized HT process for lipid feedstock conversion into biojet fuel range RH with low amount of gaseous products and high yield of liquid products, and characterize the fuel properties of obtained RH.

Research proposal will be implemented at Institute of Chemistry and Chemical Technology of Riga Technical University (Latvia).

The purpose of the DMP is to outline the strategy for data collection, storing, and sharing at all the stages of research project implementation while ensuring compliance with the legal and ethical requirements. DMP will include experimental data arranged in 2 datasets regarding to structure analyzation of novel noble metal supported catalysts (XRD, N₂-sorption analysis data) and composition analysis (GC-MS data) of produced renewable hydrocarbon mixtures via Hydrotreatment.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027

Researchers

Ilze Malina (0000-0002-2301-9674), Kristaps Malins (0000-0002-9727-0730)

Organizations
Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Development of mono and bimetallic Ru, Re catalysts for sustainable aviation fuel production (1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/064)

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Researchers:

[Ilze Malina \(0000-0002-2301-9674\)](#)

[Kristaps Malins \(0000-0002-9727-0730\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

Contact: [Malina Ilze \(Ilze.Malina_1@rtu.lv\)](mailto:Ilze.Malina_1@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027](#)

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-08-25](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Composition analysis of renewable hydrocarbon mixtures from lipid feedstocks via Hydrotreatment

Dataset will include experimental data for composition investigation of liquid renewable hydrocarbon samples produced by hydrotreatment from lipid feedstocks in the presence of newly synthesized Ru, Re and Ru-Re catalysts. DMP will include experimental data – chromatograms of liquid hydrocarbon samples. Gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (GC-MS) will be used to obtain chromatograms. Metadata such as sample IDs, sample production HT conditions, and utilized catalyst will be included. These data are necessary to determine best performing catalysts and conditions for obtaining highest liquid hydrocarbon yield and composition similar to biojet fuel.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of the data acquisition by GC-MS method is to analyze produced liquid composition of renewable hydrocarbon mixtures and investigate the specific catalyst effects on reaction pathways under HT conditions. The data will be acquired using the scientific equipment (chromatographs) available at the Institute of Chemistry and Chemical Technology (RTU).

Obtained data in the dataset will help to accomplish objectives (1) (*Synthesize, characterize and conduct catalytic screening tests of mono Ru, Re and bimetallic Ru-Re HT catalysts supported on different acidic supports*) and (2) (*Upgrade catalyst characteristics to achieve improved and reusable performance in lipid feedstock conversion into RH with biojet fuel composition*) by systematically analyzing obtained liquid hydrocarbon composition in the presence of each catalyst.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Insufficient existing metadata for liquid renewable hydrocarbon mixture composition analysis by GC-MS that are necessary for research project implementation.

Data generated in research project will be novel.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be useful to other chemists/researchers working in fields such as chemical engineering, thermochemical conversion, biofuels, catalyst materials etc.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until all the scientific publications are published.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is an open repository developed by CERN that supports multiple data types and is suitable for all scientific disciplines.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet Browser

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-07-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2030-07-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilze Malina (0000-0002-2301-9674)

GC-MS data of produced liquid hydrocarbon samples will be collected, described by metadata, organized and imported to repository by Ilze Malina.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Structure analysis of mono and bimetallic noble metal supported catalysts

Following dataset is devoted to structure investigation of novel noble metal supported catalysts synthesized within research project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/064. Novel noble metal supported catalysts will be synthesized by different methods (strong electrostatic adsorption, successive impregnation, deposit-precipitation etc.). Their structure will be analyzed by common analytical techniques.

DMP will include raw data of X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and N₂-sorption isotherms of synthesized catalysts. These data are necessary to investigate and understand catalyst structure-activity relationships and to determine most appropriate synthesis method for noble metal supported catalysts.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of the data acquisition is to analyze synthesized novel noble metal mono and bimetallic supported catalysts structure by analytical methods (XRD, N₂-sorption analysis) and therefore determine structure-catalyst activity relationships. Obtained data will help to accomplish objectives (1) (*Synthesize, characterize and conduct catalytic screening tests of mono Ru, Re and bimetallic Ru-Re HT catalysts supported on different acidic supports*) and (2) (*Upgrade catalyst characteristics to*

achieve improved and reusable performance in lipid feedstock conversion into RH with biojet fuel composition).

The data will be acquired using the scientific equipment available at the Institute of Chemistry and Chemical Technology (RTU) or at other scientific institutes within RTU.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- PNG
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Insufficient existing metadata for noble metal Ru, Re and Ru-Re catalysts supported on acidic supports that are necessary for research project implementation.

Data generated in research project will be novel.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data might be useful to other chemists/researchers working in fields such as chemical engineering, thermochemical conversion, biofuels, catalyst materials etc.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

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Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

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2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

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Until the scientific publications are published.

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2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

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2030-07-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

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3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilze Malina (0000-0002-2301-9674)

Characterization data of synthesized noble metal catalysts will be collected, described by metadata, organized and imported to repository by Ilze Malina.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

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3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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